

THE EFFECT OF TRUST BETWEEN THE DOCTOR AND THE PATIENT ON THE EFFECTIVENESS OF TREATMENT

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Abstract: Trust is one of the main characteristics of the patient-doctor relationship. He fears that rapid changes in the healthcare system will negatively affect patients' trust in doctors. Trust is a defining element of any interpersonal relationship. This is especially important in the relationship between patient and doctor.

Keywords: medicine, trust, doctor, patient, visual, sympathy, empathy, manipulation, point, attitude

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Among the professions, the profession of a medical worker and a doctor is the most delicate. Because they directly affect the health and destiny of a person. Therefore, we see that these two sides are closely related to each other, along with the culture of speech and speech etiquette. Recall the essence of the concept of indirect etiquette. Manners in general, restraint in dealing with people, morals and upbringing are his norms. Of course, the speech we have in mind is related to knowledge, spirituality and, of course, medicine. In this sense, the above ideas are important concepts reflecting the attitude of the medical professional, ethics, as well as the various relationships between doctors and patients. We see that the essence of words is the attitude of the doctor to the patient, the ability to convince him of recovery. Because trust is one of the main psychological criteria for a patient's recovery. When looking at medicine through the eyes of patients, most patients view doctors as individuals acting in their own interests, which leads to patients' distrust of treatment. Large-scale changes in the health care system have put strong pressure on this trust and could undermine it. Although there are many reviews and analyzes on trust, empirical research on patient trust is very limited, and we believe that research methods for assessing trust in the patient-physician relationship are still in the early stages of evolution. A doctor can cause a very versatile reaction in a patient. Usually, hope for recovery and confidence in professionalism prevail. Depending on the personality characteristics of a person, sympathy or antipathy, respect, a thirst for attention, a desire to communicate with people, etc. can be manifested. The success of communication with a patient

depends on the doctor's ability to correctly interpret these feelings, which ultimately affects the success of treatment.

How to talk to the patient?

According to the dominant type of perception of information in patients, visual, auditory and kinesthetic types are distinguished. This classification helps to understand patients, since communication in the doctor's office of the leading prescription system has a positive effect on the patient. It would not be an exaggeration to say that the use of this type of communication sets the stage for the formation of a working feeling.

visual images. These are the views of patients who perceive most of the information through vision. If the patient begins his speech with the words "You see, doctor", "Can you imagine ..." and uses a description of visual images in his story, then his leading communication is our receptive system. For such patients, information about their illness is related to their vision process. When communicating with such patients, the doctor explains their diseases with the help of various schemes, pictures and begins with the words "You see ...", "Pay attention ...", which directly address the leading organ of the patient. perception causes an increase in confidence.

Audials. In this type of patients, the leading receptive system is hearing, they often go to the doctor: the main rule that they adhere to is to listen. Such patients sometimes follow the speech of the doctor and involuntarily move their lips. The main factor in the formation of trust in communicating with patients is the art of explaining the patient's illness in beautiful, fluent speech. At the end of the conversation, it is helpful to repeat the patient's words: "I heard what you said..." using sentences such as "I hope you will follow my explanations."

Kinesthetic. The means of perception of these patients is their own body. They are usually very emotional, have a rich stock of gestures to express their feelings. Kinesthetics love humor and beautiful metaphors, so when explaining your situation, you can appeal to their imagination and give vivid examples. They rely more on intuition than logic and are very good at feeling other people's emotions.

The first thing a doctor does is empathize with the patient. In medical psychology, this ability is called empathy. It is very important for a doctor to learn empathy, but at the same time, one should not cross the line beyond which experiences become personal. Lack of empathy. A doctor who lacks empathy does not inspire confidence in patients. They may appear cold and unreliable, which can adversely affect treatment outcome. Too much empathy. An overly empathetic doctor may take on additional feelings, take problems to heart, and spend a lot of time listening to complaints. Patients may unconsciously exaggerate their problems when they see the excessive emotionality of the doctor, feeling sympathy for them.

Instead of achieving a positive result, such doctors can sometimes make the patient worse.

Fake empathy. Sometimes the doctor forces himself to show his feelings to the patient, as a result of which there is sincere empathy. Lack of empathy is common. The doctor is an ordinary person and cannot sincerely sympathize with everyone. In such cases, it is enough to be ready for empathy, starting with the words "Yes, I understand you ...". How to resist patient manipulation.

According to experts in the field of clinical psychology, manipulation plays an important role in relation to the patient and the doctor. This behavior is often characteristic of older patients who believe that they know better about their disease than the doctor, due to their life experience. They want certain prescriptions from the doctor, and by means of.

What factors negatively affect patient confidence?

- Cases of doing business on financial grounds can lead to a decrease in trust in doctors.

- Patients with low self-confidence, especially in cases of stress and depression, had less confidence in doctors.

-Physicians focusing on social media advertising, which are developing today, can also affect patient confidence.

- One of the most important current problems is that doctors write prescriptions in cooperation with companies, which reduces the trust of patients in the doctor.

One of the detrimental consequences of medical insecurity is that patients who experience it avoid seeking medical attention. In conclusion, since the relationship between doctor and patient is at the center of the healthcare system, there will be sincere trust between them, and the rise of medicine will continue. Patient trust is a major aspect of relationship continuity. If a patient trusts their doctor and feels they can trust you without judgment, they are more likely to provide you with information that will help you provide better care. "Medicine is a recognized art whose magic and creativity has long been manifested in the interpersonal aspects of the patient-physician relationship."

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